

Implementation of CUDA kernels with cppPosit and BFLOAT16

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1 Introduction

In today's computers, the number of computations to be performed in a second is reaching very high levels, in the order of billions of computations per second. Most of these computations are performed as floating point operations, meaning that they're performed on real numbers represented following the IEEE 754 floating point format. Researchers have noticed that this it is possible to create different formats, which are more efficient in terms of resource utilization, power consumption and memory footprint; moreover, there are some widely recognized problems with the floating point format, for example it is not portable and not fully implemented in any architecture, and also the hardware which is used for floating point computations, called FPU, is very complex and resource costing. Many different formats have been proposed, and in this work we will focus on Posit numbers and BFLOAT16, which are two formats that try to compress the representation without losing accuracy: these formats will be exploited to implement three different CUDA kernels, in particular a matrix-matrix multiplication kernel, a kernel which simulates a fully connected layer of a neural network and a convolution kernel. In Chapter 2, we will report the main components of our project, in particular we will offer an overview for posit numbers as specified in the cppPosit library, with also a brief description of the library itself, BFLOAT16, CUDA and the different operations we're going to perform. In Chapter 3, we will discuss the implementation of our project, showing snippets of the code to better explain our decisions. In Chapter 4, we will present the results we obtained. In Chapter 5, we will present our final considerations and possible improvements to be implemented.

2 Components

2.1 Posit numbers

Posit numbers and posit arithmetic were created by Gustafson and Yonemoto with the idea of introducing a format able to reduce the memory footprint by compacting the representation of the information on a smaller number of bits, maintaining therefore an accuracy close to the one of the floating point format. In particular, the idea was to reach a proper hardware support starting from application specific hardware and eventually arriving at a point where posits would have been supported in general purpose processors as well. Posits are heavily studied today as a substitute to the old floating point format by companies such as Google, Facebook, Intel and IBM.

The format for posits is a fixed-length format: a posit number is composed by 4 fields, which are the sign (represented with 1 bit), the regime field, which has variable length, the exponent field and the fraction (or mantissa) field. The last two fields are actually optional and their sizes depend on the size of the regime field, which can has a minimum length of 2 bits and a maximum length of $n - 1$ bits, where n is the number of bits used to represent the posit number. In particular, a posit number is defined giving the number of bits on which it has to be represented and the maximum number of bits on which the exponent can be defined on: for example, a posit<32,11> is a posit defined on 32 bits with an exponent which can be defined on 0 to 11 bits.

Figure 1: Illustration of a posit<32,11>

The peculiarity about posits is that they're able to give a highly accurate representation of a real number using less bits than their floating point counterpart: in fact, given a posit X , this will represent the real number r defined as:

$$r = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } X = 0 \\ NaN, & \text{if } X = -2^{nbits-1} \\ sign(X) * useed^k * 2^e * (1 + f), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

In this case, $sign(X)$ is given by the first bit of the posit representation, $useed$ is given by $2^{2^{esbits}}$, where $esbits$ is the maximum number of bits on which the exponent can be represented, e is the encoding of the exponent, f is the encoding of the fraction and k is given by the following formula:

$$k = \begin{cases} -l, & \text{if } b = 0 \\ l - 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Here, the value of k depends on the value of l , which comes from the run-length approach used to encode the regime field: in fact, l is the number of subsequent identical bits in the regime field, while b is the value of the stopping bit, which is the bit first bit in the regime field which is different from the previous ones.

Even if it may seem complex, this encoding technique allows to have a highly accurate representation of real numbers: in fact, the regime field allows to span between a high range of integer values with the help of the exponent, while the fraction field allows to have a high accuracy in the fractional part of the real number, so that the posit number can reach a very high accuracy while working on a smaller number of bits with respect to the floating point format.

Posit numbers also have a characteristic which is fundamental today, especially in neural networks: in fact, they have a tapered resolution in contrast with the flat resolution of floating point numbers, which basically means that values between -1 and 1 can be represented better with posits since there's a higher density in the amount of representations we can have for that interval with respect to the floating point case, in which the density of the representations is the same in any interval. This is very important for neural networks, since by studying the cumulative density function of the weights distribution we can notice that most of the weights must be included between -1 and 1, which is the region where posits have the highest decimal accuracy.

The main problem we encounter with posits is that, since they're a novel format, there's a lack of hardware support in general purpose processors, which means a lack of both dedicated instructions and actual hardware to support computations based on the posit representation. Due to this, we need to resort different tricks for the implementation of posits in case we're not working on posits-oriented hardware, for example exploiting the FPU to simulate a Posit Processing Unit, which is the approach that has been used for the usage of posits in our project, as we will discuss in Chapter 3.

2.2 cppPosit library

In order to implement posits inside our project, we exploited the `cppPosit` library, which provides an easy and immediate way to handle posits as any other standard C++ type. Since this library is meant to be used on general purpose processors which are not equipped with a PPU, in order to perform computations between posits the redefined operators perform an implicit conversion from *posit* to *float* to use the standard C++ operators, then a conversion from *float* back to *posit* of the result in order to obtain the final result in posit format. In this way, the library exploits the FPU, which is always present in general purpose processors, in order to perform computations.

For our project, we exploit the `cppPosit` library to implement the *posit* type; since our project was meant to be run on GPUs, we had to extend the definitions of some functions in order for them to be executed using the CUDA approach, so we will show the modifications we've performed in Chapter 3.

2.3 BFLOAT16 format

As said in Chapter 1, there are many formats which have been proposed lately as an alternative of the IEEE 754 Floating Point format, and one of these formats is called BFLOAT16, which is a 16-bit format developed by Google. BFLOAT16 is supported by many Intel, ARM and AMD processors, as well as Google Cloud TPUs, Tensorflow and CUDA.

The BFLOAT16 format is very similar to the standard floating point format, but in this case the representation is limited to 16 bits, where 1 bit is reserved to the sign, 8 bits are used for the exponent and the remaining 7 bits are used to represent the mantissa (instead of 23 as in the floating point format): this representation allows to perform conversions in an immediate way, since to convert a *float* to *BFLOAT16* it is enough to just take the 16 most significant bits of the float (which include the sign, the whole exponent and the 7 most significant bits of the mantissa), while to convert back to float it is enough to extend the mantissa to 23 bits. This standard may seem the same as FP16, which is a floating point standard used to represent a type called *half*: the difference stands in the fact that a half has 5 bits for the exponent and 10 for the mantissa, so it's not a truncation of the float as the BFLOAT16 but actually a resized version. The smaller size of the exponent of FP16 with respect to BFLOAT16 allows the former to cover a fewer interval of real numbers: the killer trait of BFLOAT16 is in fact its capability of reaching incredibly high accuracy, since with respect to float only the less significant bits of the mantissa are lost, but still managing to cover a high range of values using half of the bits of a float. For the implementation in our project of BFLOAT16, we exploited the `cuda_bfloat16`, which allows to easily define and handle a `nv_bfloat16` type as a standard C++ type, which can be used both on the host and on the GPU being this library developed by NVIDIA.

2.4 CUDA

In modern computers, CPUs are designed to excel at executing sequences of operations as fast as possible, with the capability of executing few tens of such sequences at the same time in parallel. Even if CPUs are incredibly fast nowadays, they have a huge limitation which is given by the fact that the amount of sequences, called threads, that they can run in parallel is quite limited: there are many applications, like the matrix-matrix multiplication or the convolution, which are intrinsically highly parallelizable, but which can't reach a high level of parallelization due to the nature of the CPUs.

A better device which provides a high level of parallelization is the Graphics

Processing Unit (or GPU): such component has a completely different layout, as reported in *Figure 2*, which allows to execute thousands of threads in parallel:

Figure 2: Comparison between a CPU's and a GPU's architecture

As we can see from *Figure 2*, the GPU sacrifices space reserved for the cache in the CPU in order to have much more space to be used for transistors, which will be devoted to data processing, hiding memory access latency with a speed up in computation. A CPU instead will heavily use the cache in order to avoid memory accesses, but at the same time sacrificing the possibility of highly parallelizing the computation, which is not important since CPUs are generally intended to perform well on sequential programs instead of parallel ones.

Since generally applications are a mix of sequential and parallel parts, they should exploit the CPU and GPU correctly in order to maximize the performances. In order to exploit the parallel computing power of GPUs, NVIDIA introduced CUDA in 2006: CUDA is a general purpose parallel computing platform and programming model that leverages the parallel compute engine in NVIDIA GPUs in order to solve highly parallelizable problems faster than on CPUs.

The general idea behind the CUDA parallel programming model is to exploit thread groups, also called thread blocks: each block has a set of threads and each thread is assigned to a certain portion of the input with the task of performing some computations which will give the output for that portion of the input. Each block is executed in parallel by a Streaming Multiprocessor, so that each multiprocessor can execute concurrently hundreds of threads coming from the same thread block. This approach allows to maximize the parallel capabilities of the GPU, giving at the same time to the programmer an easy reasoning approach.

2.5 Matrix-matrix multiplication

The matrix-matrix multiplication is a typical computer science problem in which we need to perform the multiplication between two matrices whose size can be particularly high. Despite not being a particularly complex problem per se, since it just needs the application of a formula to be solved, the corresponding software implementation is considered computationally heavy, since it requires

a running time of $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$, where we consider the matrices to be $n \times n$ matrices for simplicity. It is clear that this operation does not scale well, but it is not uncommon to have to perform matrix-matrix multiplications with matrices with thousands of rows and columns.

It is important to notice though that the general approach to perform matrix-matrix multiplication is highly parallelizable: in fact, each cell of the resulting matrix is equal to

$$c_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n a_{ik} * b_{kj} \quad (1)$$

The formula states that each cell of the resulting matrix is computed starting from a row and a column respectively of the first and second input matrices: this means that to compute each cell we just need to know one row and one column. It is clear that this approach can easily be parallelized: in particular, we can exploit the CUDA parallel programming model to create a parallelized algorithm in which each cell of the resulting matrix is handled by a thread, which considers one row and one column and multiplies them following the formula mentioned above to obtain the final result. In this way, the complexity is still $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$, but thanks to the parallelization the computation time highly decreases.

2.6 Fully connected kernel

Before the advent of CNNs, the most used neural network were based on fully connected layers, where each neuron in a layer is connected to all the neurons of the adjacent layers, as in the *Figure 3*:

Figure 3: Example of fully connected layers

As it is clear, this approach is not able to scale, because as the number of neurons grows the number of connections will explode, reason for which CNNs

have today replaced Multilayer Perceptron Networks, which were mainly based on this architecture.

However, fully connected layers are still widely used in CNNs as final layer to perform particular tasks like classification: in fact, a CNN for classification is typically equipped with a fully connected layer at the end, which is in charge to classify correctly the input given to the network by studying the feature description it outputs. It is therefore important to implement efficiently the operation performed by a fully connected layer, and to do so we can exploit parallelization: in fact, the activation for each neuron is given by the summation of the products of the output of each neuron in the previous layer multiplied by a weight. We can therefore think at each neuron of the resulting layer as if it is handled by a different thread, which takes as input the previous layer and the set of weights associated to that neuron: in this way, we can parallelize the computation and obtain the result in a smaller amount of time with respect to calculating everything with a sequential approach.

2.7 Convolution

Convolution is a very common operation as of today due to its wide usage in neural networks, in particular in Convolutional Neural Networks, which have the convolution as one of their main distinctive traits. The idea in CNN is to exploit convolution to avoid having fully connected layers, which require a high computational effort and do not scale well; thanks to the convolution operation, each neuron in a layer is activated by only a subset of fixed size of the neurons in the previous layer, diminishing significantly the number of operations, which allows to have deeper and more complex networks able to generally perform better than their fully connected counterparts.

Even if well performing, we need to consider that we need to perform one convolution for each neuron of a layer, and do so for each layer, so if performed sequentially this operation can take a very long time; however, it is pretty clear that this operation is highly parallelizable, since we can think to a neuron as a CUDA thread which operates on a subset of the previous layer to compute the activation. In this project, we implement a parallel convolution operation exploiting the previous idea of having one thread for each output neuron, which operates using a squared kernel.

3 Implementation

In this Chapter, we will present the details of our implementation, highlighting some crucial aspects which are important to understand how we operated and also on how to run the code to test it. We will present three versions of each kernel we presented, a float-based version, a posit-based version and a BFLOAT16-based version.

3.1 Google Colab

The first thing to highlight is that we've developed our project on Google Colab, which is a platform which provides GPUs with CUDA support. Since it is an environment originally though for Python development, we've installed the NVCC4Jupyter compiler to exploit the CUDA C++ compiler on such platform. In order to correctly upload the cppPosit library in Google Colab, we've implemented a cell which downloads the library from Google Drive, so that anyone who wants to test the library can simply run the cell to have it set up.

3.2 cppPosit modification

As mentioned in Paragraph 2.2, we used the cppPosit library to implement posits in our project. However, this library is not naturally included in the CUDA programming model and is therefore not directly usable on the GPU: in particular, the GPU will be able to handle the structures defined in the cppPosit library, but it won't be possible to exploit the functions defined in it. Since the focus of the project is to study the transfer time, we decided to redefine the functions inside cppPosit which are used for the conversion from float to posit and vice versa, so that in the GPU we can call them to convert the posits into float, perform the operations on the float and convert the result back to posit. In order to do what just said, we had to modify different function declarations between two files, the main *posit.h* file and the *bithiphop.hpp* file. The functions we modified are the following:

- *maxexponent()* and *minexponent()* from *posit.h*;
- the constructors for the *UnpackedPosit* type in *posit.h*;
- the *toFloat()* operator in *posit.h*;
- the *bitmask()* function from *bithiphop.hpp*;
- the *device_findbitleftmostC()* function from *bithiphop.hpp*;
- the *bitset_get()* function from *bithiphop.hpp*;
- the *()* operator from *bithiphop.hpp*, which is used for conversion.

The implementation of these functions remains the same as before, but we changed the definition of these functions: to be used in CUDA, they have to be defined as `__device__` or `__host__` functions, so we had them these identifiers for them to work on the GPU. The modification is always the same, so we will report one single example, in particular the modification of the `bitmask()` function defined in `bithiphop.hpp`.

```

template <typename R>
#ifdef CUDA
    __host__ __device__
        constexpr R bitmask(unsigned int const onecount)
    {
        return static_cast<R>(-(onecount != 0))
            & (static_cast<R>(-1) >>
                ((sizeof(R) * 8) - onecount));
    }
#else
    constexpr R bitmask(unsigned int const onecount)
    {
        return static_cast<R>(-(onecount != 0))
            & (static_cast<R>(-1) >>
                ((sizeof(R) * 8) - onecount));
    }
#endif

```

Listing 1: Modified version of `bitmask()` function

From *Listing 1*, we can see how to add the two aforementioned identifiers, so that the library can be used for CUDA programs as well. However, by only adding such identifiers, it would be mandatory to compile the library using the NVCC compiler for CUDA programs, but it may be useful to use the same library for any program, not only when we are running CUDA code: in particular, we would like to be able to compile code implementing the `cppPosit` library using the more common C++ compiler. In order to do so, we have to add the *if-else* statement shown in *Listing 1*: thanks to this conditional statement, we can simply add the code `"#define CUDA true"` at the beginning of all the CUDA programs we will compile using NVCC, which will define the corresponding functions in the `cppPosit` library as `__host__ __device__` following the *if* branch; if we want to create a normal C++ program which implements the `cppPosit` library and compile it with C++, we don't have to add anything to our it, since the *else* branch in *Listing 1* will be automatically followed.

3.3 Matrix-matrix multiplication

The first kernel we're going to talk about is the one performing the matrix-matrix multiplication: we will start introducing the float-based kernel, then we

will present the main differences of the posit and BFLOAT16 implementations. In this kernel, the idea is to perform a multiplication between two matrices of sizes $M*N$ and $N*W$, which will result on a final matrix of size $M*W$: such values can be modified directly inside the code, but it is suggested to keep them as a multiple of 32, since it will optimize the execution on CUDA.

For each matrix, we allocate two matrix: the first one is used in the host (therefore by the CPU) and is called host matrix, while the second is used by the device (therefore by the GPU) and is called device matrix, which are declared actually as vectors of float of size equal to the size of the corresponding matrix they have to handle for the host, while they're declared as pointers to float for the device:

```

size_t A_Bytes = M*N*sizeof(float);
size_t B_Bytes = N*W*sizeof(float);
size_t C_Bytes = M*W*sizeof(float);

vector<float> float_hA(M*N);
vector<float> float_hB(N*W);
vector<float> float_hC(M*W);

float *float_dA , *float_dB , *float_dC;
cudaMalloc(&float_dA , A_Bytes);
cudaMalloc(&float_dB , B_Bytes);
cudaMalloc(&float_dC , C_Bytes);

```

Listing 2: Memory allocation for float

As we can see from the code, it is mandatory to allocate the space on the device from the host, reason for which we have to run the *cudaMalloc()* function allocating an array of float for each matrix with the corresponding size. At this point, the A and B matrices, which are the input matrices, are randomly initialized using the following function:

```

void initialize(vector<float> &a){
    for(int i = 0; i < a.size(); i++){
        a[i] = float(rand())/float(RAND_MAX);
    }
}

```

Listing 3: Function to initialize input matrices

In this function, we generate for each cell of the input matrix a random float value between -1 and 1 to avoid the explosion of the final representation, therefore each input matrix is initialized randomly in order not to introduce any bias in the computation of the final result. Once the matrices have been initialized, they must be copied into the memory of the device we allocated previously, and we can do it with the following code:

```

cudaMemcpy( float_dA , float_hA . data ( ) ,
            A_Bytes , cudaMemcpyHostToDevice );
cudaMemcpy( float_dB , float_hB . data ( ) ,
            B_Bytes , cudaMemcpyHostToDevice );

```

Listing 4: Upload matrices from host to device

The *cudaMemcpy* function says that we need to upload the data contained in the host matrix inside the corresponding device matrix; the third parameter indicates the amount of data which we have to move, while the fourth parameter specifies that the transfer of data is performed from host to device.

At this point, we can start the configuration of the device, meaning that we need to define the number of threads for each thread block and the number of threads blocks we need to work with. In particular, we chose to use squared thread blocks of 32x32 threads: studying the result matrix, we have that the number of horizontal blocks will be equal to the horizontal size of the result matrix dividing by the number of threads per block, while the number of vertical blocks will be equal to the vertical size of the result matrix divided again by the number of threads per block, as follows:

```

int blocks_x = W / threads_x ;
int blocks_y = M / threads_x ;

dim3 threads(threads_x , threads_x );
dim3 blocks(blocks_x , blocks_y );

```

Listing 5: Initialize thread blocks

The *dim3* type is a special type which can take up to three arguments and allows to create three-dimensional blocks by specifying three different amount of threads or to specify a three-dimensional group of blocks (we need it to be two-dimensional since we're working on matrices).

At this point the initialization is completed, so we can call the kernel with the following line of code:

```

float_GEMM<<<blocks , threads>>>(float_dA , float_dB , float_dC );
cudaDeviceSynchronize ();

```

Listing 6: Kernel invocation

The angular parenthesis show that we are performing the invocation of a function which will be executed on the device: to this function we must pass the number of blocks and threads specified earlier as parameters of the angular parenthesis, while as classical parameters we pass the pointers to the device matrices containing the input matrices and the result matrix. It is important to perform the synchronization of the threads right after the invocation: if we don't do this, the CPU will resume its execution before all the threads have

completed the computation of their portion of the kernel, and the CPU will therefore eventually stop waiting for them at the following `cudaMemcpy()` invoked to move the result from the device to the host, which will therefore work as a synchronization barrier; this trick is used in many invocations, but it's reported only here for simplicity. The kernel is then defined as follows:

```

__global__ void float_GEMM(const float *a,
                          const float *b, float *c){
    int tx = threadIdx.x;
    int ty = threadIdx.y;
    int bx = blockIdx.x;
    int by = blockIdx.y;

    int row = by * blockDim.y + ty;
    int col = bx * blockDim.x + tx;

    for (int i = 0; i < N; i++){
        c[row * W + col] += a[row * N + i] * b[i * W + col];
    }
}

```

Listing 7: Kernel definition

The kernel is defined as a `__global__` function, which is a declaration defined by the CUDA parallel programming model which states that such function can be invoked by the host and will be executed on the device. In this function, the first thing we do is to retrieve the horizontal and vertical indices of the thread and the block by exploiting a built-in structure: these indices are used to compute the row of the first input matrix and the column of the second input matrix which will have to be multiplied one to the other, since as said one thread will handle just one column and one row to get the result for one single cell of the final matrix. In the for cycle, we simply perform the multiplication of all the cells and the summation of them, saving the result in the corresponding cell of the result matrix.

Once all the threads have terminated their task, the device matrix `c` will contain the final result of the matrix multiplication operation: to retrieve such result in the host, we can run again a `cudaMemcpy` function, which goes in the opposite direction of the instances run previously, therefore copying device memory into the host memory:

```

cudaMemcpy(float_hC.data(), float_dC,
           C_Bytes, cudaMemcpyDeviceToHost);

```

Listing 8: Move result matrix from device to host

In this way, `float_hC` will contain the result matrix containing data in the `float` format.

We can now see how the posit matrix multiplication has been implemented: first of all, it is necessary to include the `cppPosit` library, state that we're using the `posit` namespace and define a `posit` type, which in our implementation is called *realPosit*. This can be done by the following three lines of code:

```
#include "/content/Project/cppPosit/include/posit.h"

using namespace posit;

typedef posit::Posit<int16_t, nbits, esbits, uint16_t,
    posit::PositSpec::WithNaN> realPosit;
```

Listing 9: Creation of *realPosit* type

To define a `posit`, we need the following arguments: a signed integer type whose size in bits is the same as the one of the `posit` we want to create; the number of bits *nbits* on which we want our `posit` to be defined; the maximum number of bits *esbits* that can be reserved for the exponent; a *uintX_t* type which is needed from the library; a specifier which is an enumerate, defined with the `PositSpec` namespace, that can assume one of the values *WithNaN*, *WithInf* or *WithNaNInf*.

Given the new *realPosit* type, we can define the host and device matrices for the `posit` as done previously for the float version:

```
size_t A_Posit_Bytes = M*N*sizeof(realPosit);
size_t B_Posit_Bytes = N*W*sizeof(realPosit);
size_t C_Posit_Bytes = M*W*sizeof(realPosit);

vector<realPosit> posit_hA(M*N);
vector<realPosit> posit_hB(N*W);
vector<realPosit> posit_hC(M*W);

realPosit *posit_dA, *posit_dB; realPosit *posit_dC;
cudaMalloc(&posit_dA, A_Posit_Bytes);
cudaMalloc(&posit_dB, B_Posit_Bytes);
cudaMalloc(&posit_dC, C_Posit_Bytes);
```

Listing 10: Memory allocation for `posit`

At this point, instead of initializing the matrices from scratch as done for floats, we decided to implement a conversion of the float matrix to a `posit` matrix in order to have the same values in both cases, which would make testing more significant. The conversion function is the following:

```
void convertToPosit(vector<float> floatMatrix,
    vector<realPosit> &positMatrix){
```

```

    for(int i = 0; i < floatMatrix.size(); i++){
        positMatrix[i] = realPosit (floatMatrix[i]);
    }
}

```

Listing 11: Function to convert floats to posit

In this function we simply iterate over the float matrix and convert each value to a posit one by using the default constructor for posit numbers.

After conversion, we moved the values from the posit host matrix to the posit device matrix, which can be done exploiting the *cudaMalloc()* function as done for floats. At this point, we invoked the kernel, which has been redefined for the posit type, as follows:

```

float *holder_float_dA , *holder_float_dB , *holder_float_dC ;
cudaMalloc(&holder_float_dA , A_Bytes);
cudaMalloc(&holder_float_dB , B_Bytes);
cudaMalloc(&holder_float_dC , C_Bytes);

posit_GEMM<<<1, 1>>>(posit_dA , posit_dB , posit_dC ,
                    holder_float_dA , holder_float_dB , holder_float_dC );

```

Listing 12: Posit kernel invocation

In this case, we can see two main differences with respect to the float case: the first difference is that we have to use three vectors of floats named holders, which will take the converted posit matrices to perform operations over them, since we don't redefine the posit operations for CUDA; the second difference is that in this case the kernel is invoked with one block and one thread, which is useful to then exploit the original matrix multiplication kernel defined for floats. The implementation of the *posit.GEMM()* kernel is the following:

```

__global__ void posit_GEMM(const realPosit *a,
                          const realPosit *b, realPosit *c,
                          float *float_dA , float *float_dB ,
                          float *float_dC){

    int blocks_x = W / threads_x;
    int blocks_y = M / threads_x;

    dim3 threads(threads_x , threads_x);
    dim3 blocks(blocks_x , blocks_y);

    convertToFloat<<<1, 2>>>(a, b, float_dA ,float_dB );
    cudaDeviceSynchronize();
    __syncthreads();
    float_GEMM<<<blocks , threads>>>(float_dA ,float_dB ,float_dC );
    cudaDeviceSynchronize();
    __syncthreads();
}

```

```

    toPositArray<<<blocks , threads>>>(float_dC , W, c);
    cudaDeviceSynchronize ();
    __syncthreads ();
}

```

Listing 13: Posit kernel implementation

As we can see, in this case we have the kernel calling the *float_GEMM()* kernel with a number of blocks and threads equal to the ones used for the normal invocation of the kernel: the posit kernel is therefore just a wrapper kernel, where we perform the conversion of the posit matrices once they've been moved to the device, making them floats so that we can invoke the float matrix multiplication kernel over them; the result is then converted back to posits, so that it can eventually be moved back to the device at the end of the execution of the posit kernel. It is important to highlight that the *convertToFloat()* kernel is invoked 1 block and 2 threads, and the reason is clear if we consider the implementation of the kernel itself:

```

__global__ void convertToFloat(const realPosit *a,
                              const realPosit *b, float *dA, float *dB){
    if (threadIdx.x == 0){
        int blocks_x = N / threads_x;
        int blocks_y = M / threads_x;

        dim3 threads(threads_x , threads_x);
        dim3 blocks(blocks_x , blocks_y);
        toFloatArray<<<blocks , threads>>>(a,N,dA);
    }
    else{
        int blocks_x = W / threads_x;
        int blocks_y = N / threads_x;

        dim3 threads(threads_x , threads_x);
        dim3 blocks(blocks_x , blocks_y);
        toFloatArray<<<blocks , threads>>>(b,W,dB);
    }
}

```

Listing 14: Conversion from posit to float

The idea of this function is to have two different threads, one which will handle the conversion of the first input matrix and the second which will convert the other input matrix: it is important to remember that the two matrices do not have the same size, therefore the number of blocks which can be defined over them will be different, for which reason we have to recompute *blocks* and *threads* inside each thread. The *toFloatArray()* function is the dual of the *toPositArray()* function, where the idea is to take the row and the column of the cell of the matrix which is handled by the corresponding thread and perform a simple

conversion respectively from posit to float and vice versa.

Once the *posit_GEMM()* kernel has completed its execution, we will have the result matrix in *posit_dC*, so we can retrieve it from the device exploiting the *cudaMemcpy()* function as done in the float case.

The last portion of the kernel implementation is reserved to the implementation of the BFLOAT16 type and its usage to perform matrix multiplication. In this case, we exploited the *cuda_bf16.h* library, which allows to use the *nv_bfloat16* type both on the host and on the device. However, even if this library is supported by CUDA, we noticed that the operations were not working correctly, therefore we had to perform the same trick we used for posits, converting the numbers to float, performing the operations with the converted numbers and then converting the result back to BFLOAT16: in particular, this was an hardware-related problem, since the CUDA capability of the GPUs provided by Google Colab was below *sm_53*, which is the minimum CUDA capability to perform operations such as *_hmul*.

Passing to the implementation, first of all we had to create the host matrix and the device matrix:

```
#include <cuda_bf16.h>

size_t A_Bfloat_Bytes = M*N*sizeof(nv_bfloat16);
size_t B_Bfloat_Bytes = N*W*sizeof(nv_bfloat16);
size_t C_Bfloat_Bytes = M*W*sizeof(nv_bfloat16);

vector<nv_bfloat16> bfloat_hA (M*N);
vector<nv_bfloat16> bfloat_hB (N*W);
vector<nv_bfloat16> bfloat_hC (M*W);

nv_bfloat16 *bfloat_dA , *bfloat_dB , *bfloat_dC ;
cudaMalloc(&bfloat_dA , A_Bfloat_Bytes );
cudaMalloc(&bfloat_dB , B_Bfloat_Bytes );
cudaMalloc(&bfloat_dC , C_Bfloat_Bytes );
```

Listing 15: Memory allocation for BFLOAT16

The approach is again the same for the memory allocation, and as we did for posit we also initialize the input matrices by converting the original float matrices, with a function *convertToBfloat()* which is equivalent to the *convertToPosit()* function, with the same implementation. Once the matrices are ready, the values are again moved to the device with the *cudaMemcpy()* function; after this, the kernel for the BFLOAT16 format is invoked as follows:

```
bfloat_GEMM<<<blocks , threads>>>(bfloat_dA , bfloat_dB , bfloat_dC );
```

Listing 16: BFLOAT16 kernel invocation

In this case, we noticed there was no need to use a wrapper kernel, therefore we resorted to invoking the kernel as in the float case. The implementation of the BFLOAT16 kernel is then very similar to the implementation of the float

kernel, with the difference that we have to handle two conversions to perform the operations using float numbers instead of BFLOAT16 numbers:

```

__global__ void bfloat_GEMM(const nv_bfloat16 *x,
                           const nv_bfloat16 *w, nv_bfloat16 *y){
    int tx = threadIdx.x;
    int ty = threadIdx.y;
    int bx = blockIdx.x;
    int by = blockIdx.y;

    int row = by * blockDim.y + ty;
    int col = bx * blockDim.x + tx;

    float res = 0.0f;
    for (int i = 0; i < N; i++){
        res += (float)x[row * N + i] * (float)w[i * W + col];
    }
    y[row * W + col] = (nv_bfloat16) res;
}

```

Listing 17: BFLOAT16 kernel implementation

As we can see from *Listing 17*, we need to perform the conversion of the matrices x and w inside the float in order to perform the computation of the contributions of the corresponding row and column; such contribution, which is defined as a float, is then converted to BFLOAT16 in order to have the correct format in the resulting matrix.

During the execution of the kernels, different timings have been computed in order for them to be compared later on; moreover, we decided to also compute the memory footprint of the matrices and the accuracy of the results. All these information are reported in Chapter 4.

3.4 Fully Connected Layer

The implementation of the fully connected layer uses some functions which are very similar to the functions used for matrix multiplication, therefore repeated implementations won't be reported. Moreover, the general structure of the implementation of each kernel is the same, therefore we will focus in this report only on the main points we have to highlight in terms of code and thought process.

In our project, we implemented a fully connected operation where a layer with N neurons was connected to a following layer of M neurons, therefore requiring a weight matrix of size $N*M$. The memory allocation and initialization of the matrices are the same as in the matrix multiplication kernel, so we allocated host matrices and devices matrices, initializing the float host matrices from scratch while the posit and BFLOAT16 matrices have been initialized starting from the

corresponding float matrices: the data contained into the host input matrices have then been moved to the device matrices exploiting the *cudaMemcpy()* function, after which the corresponding kernel have been invoked.

The kernels have different implementations, therefore we will study them one by one, starting with the float implementation, which is invoked and is defined as follows:

```
fullyConnected<<<1, 1>>>(dX, dW, dWT, dY);

__global__ void fullyConnected(const float *x,
                               const float *W, float *dWT, float *y){

    int blocks_x = M / threads_x;
    int blocks_y = (N+1) / threads_x;

    dim3 threads(threads_x, threads_x);
    dim3 blocks(blocks_x, blocks_y);

    Transpose<<<blocks, threads>>>(W, dWT);
    cudaDeviceSynchronize();
    __syncthreads();
    Dot<<<blocks, threads>>>(x, dWT, y);
    cudaDeviceSynchronize();
    __syncthreads();
}
```

Listing 18: Float kernel invocation and implementation

For this kernel, we exploited the same approach of using a wrapper kernel as we did for the posit matrix multiplication, therefore the float kernel for the fully connected operation is invoked by passing the pointers to 4 float matrices, where x is the input layer, w is the weight matrix, WT is a matrix which will contain the transpose of the weight matrix (which is required to compute the result) and y is the matrix which will hold the final result of the operation. We can easily notice that the transpose is an operation which can be parallelized: in particular, we decided to assign a thread to each cell of the transpose matrix, so that in the implementation it would've been enough to take the value of a certain cell from the original weight matrix and use it in the transposed cell, as follows:

```
__global__ void Transpose(const float *w, float *wT){
    int tx = threadIdx.x;
    int ty = threadIdx.y;
    int bx = blockIdx.x;
    int by = blockIdx.y;

    int row = by * blockDim.y + ty;
```

```

    int col = bx * blockDim.x + tx;

    wT[col * (N+1) + row] = w[row * M + col];
}

```

Listing 19: Transpose operation over floats

Once computed the transpose, we need to actually perform the fully connected operation: the idea in this case is to associate a thread to each cell of the transpose of the weight matrix, since in this way the neuron of the resulting layer which must be handled by the thread is simply given by tx reported in *Listing 20*, while the input layer must be completely visited each time. After associating the thread, to obtain the result for each output neuron we add to compute the summation of the products between the input layer and the corresponding column of the transpose of the weight vector. This operation is performed by the *Dot()* kernel, which takes as input the input layer and the transpose of the weight matrix previously computed and calculates for each thread the aforementioned contribution to the result layer. The implementation of the *Dot()* kernel is the following:

```

__global__ void Dot(const float *x, const float *W, float *y){
    int tx = threadIdx.x + blockIdx.x * blockDim.x;
    float sum = 0;
    for (int i = 0; i < N+1; i++){
        sum += x[i] * W[tx*(N+1)+i];
    }
    y[tx] = sum;
}

```

Listing 20: Dot product for floats

After the execution of the *Dot()* kernel, the y vector will contain the result of the fully connected operation, which can therefore be moved from the device to the host exploiting once again the *cudaMemcpy()* operation.

For what concerns the implementation of the fully connected operation exploiting posits, the same considerations that have been stated for the matrix multiplication operation hold here, as well as the same workflow saw for the float fully connected operation. After the memory allocation and the conversion from float to posit for the initialization of the matrices, the posit kernel for the operation is invoked as follows:

```

float *holder_dX , *holder_dW , *holder_dY , *holder_dWT;
cudaMalloc(&holder_dX , X_Bytes);
cudaMalloc(&holder_dW , W_Bytes);
cudaMalloc(&holder_dY , Y_Bytes);
cudaMalloc(&holder_dWT , W_Bytes);

```

```

posit_fullyConnected<<<1, 1>>>(posit_dX , posit_dW , posit_dY ,
                               holder_dX , holder_dW ,

```

```
holder_dY , holder_dWT );
```

Listing 21: Posit kernel invocation

As for the posit version of the matrix multiplication kernel, here we use a set of *holders*, which are vectors and matrices of floats to be used to perform the computations after that the posit have been converted to floats on the device. Again, we can see how we are invoking a wrapper kernel by passing only one thread and one block. The kernel is then implemented as follows:

```
--global__ void posit_fullyConnected(
    const realPosit *x, const realPosit *W, realPosit *y,
    float *float_dX , float *float_dW ,
    float *float_dY , float *float_dWT){

    int blocks_x = M / threads_x;

    convertToFloat<<<1, 2>>>(x, W, float_dX ,float_dW );
    cudaDeviceSynchronize ();
    __syncthreads ();
    fullyConnected<<<1, 1>>>(float_dX ,float_dW ,float_dWT ,float_dY );
    cudaDeviceSynchronize ();
    __syncthreads ();
    toPositArray<<<blocks_x , threads_x>>>(float_dY , M, y);
    cudaDeviceSynchronize ();
    __syncthreads ();
}
```

Listing 22: Posit kernel implementation

The approach used in this case is exactly the same as the one used for the posit version of the matrix multiplication kernel: the *convertToFloat()* kernel is defined over two threads, each one in charge of the conversion of one of the two inputs, with the same definition we had for the matrix multiplication kernel; once that we have the float version of the inputs, the *fullyConnected()* kernel is invoked, and since it is a wrapper kernel itself we just need to pass 1 block and 1 thread; when the result has been computed and stored inside the holder *float_dY*, the *toPositArray()* kernel is invoked to convert it back to posits, which are eventually transferred back to the host after the completion of the *posit_fullyConnected()* kernel by using the *cudaMemcpy()* function.

The implementation of the BFLOAT16 kernel is again very similar to the previous two, so we start by allocating the memory and initializing the inputs by conversion from the float matrices. Once the data are loaded on the device, the BFLOAT16 kernel is invoked as follows:

```
bfloat_fullyConnected<<<1, 1>>>(bfloat_dX ,
    bfloat_dW , bfloat_dWT , bfloat_dY );
```

Listing 23: BFLOAT16 kernel invocation

Once again, the kernel is defined as a wrapper kernel; as for the matrix multiplication case, we don't need holders in this case since the conversion is performed on the fly inside the kernel. The BFLOAT16 kernel is defined exactly as the float kernel:

```

__global__ void bfloat_fullyConnected(const nv_bfloat16 *x,
                                     const nv_bfloat16 *W,
                                     nv_bfloat16 *dWT,
                                     nv_bfloat16 *y){

    int blocks_x = M / threads_x;
    int blocks_y = (N+1) / threads_x;
    dim3 threads(threads_x, threads_x);
    dim3 blocks(blocks_x, blocks_y);

    bfloat_Transpose<<<blocks, threads>>>(W, dWT);
    cudaDeviceSynchronize();
    __syncthreads();
    bfloat_Dot<<<blocks, threads>>>(x, dWT, y);
    cudaDeviceSynchronize();
    __syncthreads();
}

```

Listing 24: BFLOAT16 kernel invocation

The idea behind this kernel is exactly the same of the one for the float kernel, for which we compute the transpose of the weight matrix and then we perform the dot product of the input layer with the transpose matrix: however, the transpose kernel and the dot kernel have to be redefined to support the BFLOAT16 type, in particular the *bfloat.Dot()* kernel performs a conversion from BFLOAT16 to float to perform the computation, saving the final result as BFLOAT16 and therefore performing the opposite conversion.

3.5 Convolution

The third type of kernel we've implemented allows to perform a convolution operation: in particular, given an input layer of size $N*N$ and a weight matrix of size $k*k$, it allows to perform a convolution operation returning an $N*N$ matrix, with the convolution having zero-padding and stride equal to 1. As already mentioned in Paragraph 3.4, the workflow is very similar to the previous cases and many functions have been reused (for example, the function used to compute the transpose of a matrix, both for floats and BFLOAT16), therefore in this report we will focus on the main differences, but still giving an overview of the entire implementation.

Starting with the description of the implementation of the float version of the kernel, we first of all allocate the memory and initialize the matrices as saw for the previous kernels. After initialization, we load the data into the device matrices, then we invoke the convolution kernel as follows:

```

int blocks_x = N / threads_x;
int blocks_y = N / threads_x;

dim3 threads(threads_x, threads_x);
dim3 blocks(blocks_x, blocks_y);

convolution<<<<blocks, threads>>>(dX, dW, dWT, dY);

```

Listing 25: Float kernel invocation

Differently from the fully connected kernel, in this case we don't have a wrapper kernel, but an actual kernel performing the convolution operation: in particular, a different cell of the resulting matrix is assigned to each thread, which will therefore need to handle the the transpose of the weight matrix and the $k*k$ portion of the input matrix which is associated to the corresponding neuron of the output matrix. The implementation of the kernel is the following:

```

__global__ void convolution(const float *x, float* dW,
                          float *dWT, float *y){
    int tx = threadIdx.x;
    int ty = threadIdx.y;
    int bx = blockIdx.x;
    int by = blockIdx.y;

    int row = by * blockDim.y + ty;
    int col = bx * blockDim.x + tx;

    dim3 blocks(1,1);
    dim3 threads(k,k);

    Transpose<<<<blocks, threads>>>(dW, dWT);
    cudaDeviceSynchronize();
    __syncthreads();

    float sum = 0;

    int row_i = row - k/2;
    int col_i = col - k/2;

    for(int i = 0; i < k; i++){
        //check if we're on a vertex of the input matrix
        //or on an edge to apply the correct padding

        //compute the contribution of each cell and
        //add it to the accumulator "sum"
    }
    y[row * N + col] = sum;

```

```
}
```

Listing 26: Float kernel implementation

For the sake of simplicity, *Listing 26* does not report the exact code to compute the convolution, since it is too complex to show here and not so meaningful overall, since it's mostly performing the correct indexing. It is important to highlight the reasoning behind the code: to perform padding, we checked if we were in a corner of the input layer or eventually on an edge; based on our position, we applied zero-padding by simply adding only the contributions given by the cells of the input matrix which were covered by the weight matrix as well, considering that the cells of the weight matrix falling out of the input matrix would've had been multiplied by zero and would've not contributed to the final result.

Beside this consideration over the computation of the convolution operation, we can say that in this kernel we also perform the transposition of the weight matrix, which is therefore performed concurrently by each thread, which does not introduce any particular delay since the matrix is very small. The *Transpose()* kernel is exactly the same we used for the fully connected operations, therefore it won't be reported again here.

Once the convolution has been completed, the result layer can be obtained from the device memory exploiting the *cudaMemcpy()* function.

For what concerns the posit implementation of the convolution operation, the reasoning is exactly the same as before: the difference though stands in how the kernel is implemented and invoked, since in this case we consider a wrapper kernel which is called from the host as follows:

```
float *holder_dX , *holder_dW , *holder_dY , *holder_dWT ;
cudaMalloc(&holder_dX , X_Bytes );
cudaMalloc(&holder_dW , W_Bytes );
cudaMalloc(&holder_dY , Y_Bytes );
cudaMalloc(&holder_dWT , W_Bytes );

posit_convolution <<<1, 1>>>(posit_dX , posit_dW , posit_dY ,
                             holder_dX , holder_dW , holder_dY , holder_dWT );
```

Listing 27: Posit kernel invocation

Once again for posits, we need to exploit holders, which will temporarily contain the converted matrices from posit to float inside the device, during the execution of the kernel. The *posit_convolution()* kernel is therefore a wrapper kernel function, which is implemented as follows:

```
--global-- void posit_convolution(const realPosit *x,
                                  const realPosit *W, realPosit *y,
                                  float *float_dX , float *float_dW ,
                                  float *float_dY , float *float_dWT){

    int blocks_x = N / threads_x;
```

```

int blocks_y = N / threads_x;

dim3 threads(threads_x , threads_x);
dim3 blocks(blocks_x , blocks_y);

convertToFloat<<<1, 2>>>(x, W, float_dX ,float_dW );
cudaDeviceSynchronize ();
__syncthreads ();
convolution<<<blocks , threads>>>(float_dX ,float_dW ,
                                float_dWT ,float_dY );

cudaDeviceSynchronize ();
__syncthreads ();
toPositArray<<<blocks , threads>>>(float_dY , N, y);
cudaDeviceSynchronize ();
__syncthreads ();
}

```

Listing 28: Posit kernel implementation

As shown in *Listing 28*, the workflow is exactly the same of the other kernel implementations for posits, with the idea of converting the posit matrices to float matrices, perform the computations over the latter and convert the final result back to posit.

For what concerns the BFLOAT16 implementation, the same considerations can be done, therefore we will report only the invocation since the code of the implementation is exactly the same of the float version, with the difference that it has explicit conversions from BFLOAT16 to float and vice versa when performing operations (it also requires the redefinition of the *Transpose()* kernel, which is though exactly the same in the implementation of the *Transpose()* kernel for BFLOAT16 mentioned in Paragraph 3.4):

```

bfloat_convolution<<<blocks , threads>>>(bfloat_dX ,
                                bfloat_dW , bfloat_dWT , bfloat_dY );

```

Listing 29: BFLOAT16 kernel invocation

4 Results

In this section, we will report the results we've obtained with our project. In particular, we will report the results in terms of accuracy of each of the methods, which is the error each representation has compared to the floating point representation; we will also report some timings, like the conversion times, computation times and transfer times; finally, we will highlight the memory footprint of each method, to study the requirement each one has in terms of memory. We also try to test different type of posits, as we will shown later in the Chapter. In order to collect the error due to the compression which causes a shift in the value of the representation and therefore a degradation of the accuracy, we implemented a function which computes the contribution to the total error for each cell of the resulting matrix, as follows:

```
void measureCompressionError(vector<float> correctResult ,
                             vector<nv_bfloat16> approxResult){
    float error = 0;
    float maxError = 0;
    float minError = FLT_MAX;
    float avgError = 0;
    for (int i = 0; i < correctResult.size(); i++){
        float contrib = abs(correctResult[i]-
                            _bfloat16float(approxResult[i]))
                        /abs(correctResult[i]);
        if (correctResult[i] == 0){
            contrib = abs(correctResult[i]-
                            _bfloat16float(approxResult[i]));
        }
        error += contrib;
        if (contrib > maxError) maxError = contrib;
        if (contrib < minError) minError = contrib;
    }
    avgError = error / correctResult.size();
    cout << "Avg_Error_Bfloat:_" << avgError << endl;
    cout << "Max_Error_Bfloat:_" << maxError << endl;
    cout << "Min_Error_Bfloat:_" << minError << endl;
}
```

Listing 30: BFLOAT16 kernel invocation

This implementation is the one which compares a vector of floats with a vector of BFLOAT16, but there's also a parallel implementation which works in the same way but allows the comparison between floats and posits. In the for cycle, we compute the normalized contribution of each cell of the resulting matrix, converting the BFLOAT16 value to a float value first; in case the correct result, therefore the correct float value, is equal to 0 (which is possible, since the value we generate for the floats are in the interval $[-1, 1]$), then we simply add the error as a non-normalized contribution. We can therefore consider the average error

as an average distance measure between the float result and the approximated result coming from the other formats. For each cell, we also check if we have to update the maximum error and the minimum error, which are considered on a single cell. The total error given by the sum of all the contributions is then divided by the size of the matrix to return the average error introduced by the conversion. The error for the posit type is computed in the exact same way. For what concerns the registration of the timings, we compute the following timings:

- Conversion time, which is the time needed for the conversion of all inputs either from float to posit or from float to BFLOAT16;
- Operands Transfer Time, which is the time needed to transfer the inputs from the host to the device, either in their compressed form (BFLOAT16 or posit) or in the uncompressed format (float);
- Computation time, which is the time needed for the execution of the kernel function;
- Result transfer time, which is the time needed to transfer the result from the device to the host.

To compute such time intervals, we exploit the *time.h* and *ctime* libraries, defining two *clock_t* variables called *start* and *stop*, using the function *clock()* to take the timestamp in certain spots of the program and allowing us to compute the elapsed time as a difference of the two.

Finally, we've also recorded the memory footprint of each kernel, computing the amount of bytes which must be moved from host to device and vice versa to perform the operations. In order to do so, we exploit the variables tagged with the keyword *Bytes*, which represent the size of the different matrices, as reported in *Listing 2*: such variables are used to allocate space in the device for the corresponding matrices, therefore they represent the amount of bytes needed for each of them.

It is important to highlight that the tests in the following paragraphs have been performed all with the same matrices and vectors across different setups, in order to make sure there is no bias inserted by the random generation of the input data.

4.1 Matrix multiplication

For the matrix multiplication kernel, we collected the results for posit<8,0>, posit<8,1>, posit<8,2>, posit<8,4>, posit<16,0>, posit<16,2>, posit<16,4> and posit<16,8>, and we tested each of them considering for simplicity two squared matrices of size equal to 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024 and 2048 for each dimension. Starting from the error, we can plot a graph that shows the average error as we increase the size of the matrix.

From *Figure 4*, we can see how the error for the float is always equal to 0, since it is the base over which we compute the error itself. For the graph, we

Figure 4: Average error on the result of the matrix multiplication

picked for posits only the generally best performing ones in our tests, one for the posit encoded with 8 bits and one for the posit encoded with 16 bits. The graph shows how the error for the posit encoded on 8 bits is substantially higher than the error obtained with the other two formats: this of course comes from the fact that the posit is in this case represented on one fourth of the bits on which the float is represented, hence the difference in representational capability. At the same time, we can see that the other formats perform really well, in particular the posit<16,0>, which is able to achieve an almost negligible error, while the error obtained with BFLOAT16 may result relevant in some cases. It is though important to study this graph along with the one of the memory footprint, which is reported in *Figure 5*, where we have again the matrix dimension on the x-axis and the number of bytes on the y-axis.

Figure 5: Memory footprint of the matrix multiplication

In this graph, the posit on 16 bits and the BFLOAT16 have the exact same value, therefore the posit<16,0> does not actually appear; moreover, for matrix size lower than 256, it seems like there's no difference, which is caused by the scale of the graph. In all the cases, the memory footprint for the float tests is twice as big as the memory footprint of posit<16,0> and BFLOAT16: this is expected since the float is defined on twice the amount of bits. As we therefore should expect, the posit<8,0> is the one with lower memory footprint, since it

is defined on half the bits of BFLOAT16 and $\text{posit}\langle 16,0 \rangle$: however, as we saw in *Figure 4*, a posit defined on 8 bit has a significant error, therefore the usage of $\text{posit}\langle 16,- \rangle$ against $\text{posit}\langle 8,- \rangle$ should be application specific, so that if the error should be minimized the former must be preferred, while if we have a certain margin of error (like in neural networks), it may be better to use the latter in order to decrease the memory footprint. Notice that in *Figure 5* we reported again one posit encoded on 8 bits and one encoded in 16 bits, but they're not the best performing in terms of memory footprint, since there's no difference between the different posits encoded in 8 bits or 16 bits: the memory footprint depends on the total size of the posit, not on the maximum amount of bits reserved for the exponent!

We need though to highlight that, following our tests, we noticed that the decrease in the memory footprint does not match, for posits, a decrease in the total time necessary to complete the operation, as we can see from *Figure 6*, where we represent again the matrix dimension on the x-axis and the seconds on the y-axis.

Figure 6: Total time to get the result of the matrix multiplication

In this graph, the posits have the same timing as the float, so only $\text{posit}\langle 16,- \rangle$, which is the average between the different posits encoded on 16 bits we tried, is reported. It is interesting to notice that there's no difference in the total time needed to perform the operation with posits and floats, while there is a substantial difference between BFLOAT16 and all the rest when using matrices of size greater or equal to 512: this seems to be playing in favor of such format, since it is the one which is able to achieve a similar result to float in terms of accuracy, in a smaller amount of time and with a half of memory footprint. To understand why this happens, it is though important to understand how we obtain such timing, so we can study *Figure 7*, *Figure 8* and *Figure 9*, which report the Operands Transfer Time, the Result Transfer Time and the Compute Time, with the conversion time not considered since it is negligible.

Figure 7: Operands Transfer Time of the matrix multiplication

Figure 8: Result Transfer Time of the matrix multiplication

Let's start by studying *Figure 7*, which again has the size of the matrix on the x-axis and the seconds on the y-axis. In this case, we can see how the transfer time required for the float time is significantly higher, which is compelling to the fact that the memory footprint is very high for floats; at the same time, the transfer time for BFLOAT16 and posit<16,> is basically the same, since they both have the same memory footprint, while the transfer time for posit<8,> is the lowest one. It is interesting to highlight that the transfer time of BFLOAT16 and posit<16,> is twice as big the transfer time for posit<8,>, while the transfer time for floats is around four times the transfer time for posit<8,>, which correspond to the proportion of the memory footprint. However, we can also notice that the transfer time for the operands is always very small compared to the total time, therefore it doesn't impact too much the final result.

We can therefore study *Figure 8*, which shows the Result Transfer Time: as seen for the operands, the transfer time is proportional to the memory footprint, with floats requiring twice the amount of time to perform the transfer with respect to BFLOAT16 and posit<16,> and four times the amount of time that posit<8,> needs. It is also interesting to highlight that, since we're moving one matrix in this case instead of two, the Result Transfer Time in each text is always about the same as half of the Operands Transfer Time, which is what we

should expect since half of the bytes are moved in this case. Again though, the time required for the transfer is very small, negligible if compared to the total time, therefore it is not important for the final result.

Finally, we can check *Figure 9*, which shows the Computation Time for the matrix multiplication: the graph actually shows only BFLOAT16 and posit<16,->, since the former overlaps the float results and the posit<8,-> results in an almost perfect match.

Figure 9: Computation Time of the matrix multiplication

These results are again somewhat expected: in fact, the posits are converted during the computation into floats, over which the actual operations are performed, meaning that we are basically performing the same operations which therefore require the same time; with BFLOAT16 though we have support from CUDA itself, which allows us to have faster computations, therefore we obtain a smaller time, which is though not exactly half of the time of the float format probably due to the fact that the support for BFLOAT16 is still not perfect. It is also important to highlight that we don't have a higher time with posits despite the presence of conversion because the conversion time is negligible, therefore the timings are basically the same.

As a final result, we can say that BFLOAT16 proves to be the best choice in this case, because it is able to reduce the memory footprint and the total computation time without losing too much in accuracy; however, with the proper hardware support from CUDA to posits, we could expect to have similar results for posit<16,-> and even better results in terms of timing and memory footprint for posit<8,->, even if in this last case the accuracy of the result may be too severely affected. It is also important to highlight that, for matrix sizes lower than 128, there's basically no difference in timings between floats, BFLOAT16 and posit<16,->, which only differ by their memory footprint, while posit<8,-> still has some accuracy degradation to take into consideration.

4.2 Fully Connected

For the fully connected operation, we performed the same tests as we did for the matrix multiplication operation, on the same formats as before.

We can again starting our study from the average error, which is represented in *Figure 10*.

Figure 10: Average error on the result of the fully connected

We can see that the results obtained on the average error are still complaint to what we should expect from the error: in particular, we can see that posit<8,-> has a significant error which tends to increase as the matrix size increases, as it happens for the matrix multiplication operation; the error for BFLOAT16 is instead lower, but it's still higher than the error we have for posit<16,->, which almost perfectly approximate the result obtained by the float format.

For what concerns the memory footprint, we have again the same results as obtained before for the matrix multiplication, as shown in *Figure 11*.

Figure 11: Memory footprint of the fully connected

We can easily see that the results are exactly the same as for the matrix multiplication, with the float format moving twice the amount of bytes compared to the BFLOAT16 and posit<16,-> formats and four times the amount of bytes compared to the posit<8,-> format. However, since now we are dealing with fully connected layers, we have to move two one-dimensional vectors and a matrix instead of three matrices, resulting in much lower memory footprint with respect to the matrix multiplication case.

This last consideration heavily reflects on the results obtained on the timings, which are reported in *Figure 12*.

Figure 12: Total time to get the result of the fully connected

As we can see, it looks like all the timings are exactly the same, which may seem wrong at first sight: if we consider the memory footprint for the matrix multiplication from *Figure 5* along with the memory footprint for the fully connected operation from *Figure 11* though, we can notice that when dealing with a size of 2048 in the fully connected case we have to deal with more or less the same amount of bytes that we have to handle with a matrix size equal to 1024 in the matrix multiplication case; if we now check *Figure 6* with the timings for the matrix multiplication, we can easily notice that for a matrix size of 1024 there is almost no difference between the different types, meaning that it may be useful to run the test on the fully connected operation with a higher dimension for the matrix in order to obtain more significant results (we didn't run such tests since they were particularly slow from this point on).

It is important mentioning that the timings for the operands and result transfer reflect exactly the timings we found for the matrix multiplication operation, therefore we don't report the graphs in the report; for what concerns the computation time, it is again the most contributing part of the total time and the graph is identical to the one of the latter, so we decided not to report it as well to avoid redundancy.

To sum up the results, we can say that the memory footprint plays again in favor of the alternative formats, which is the same that happens for the matrix multiplication operation. For what concerns the average error, we have again the same situation as in the matrix multiplication case, since posit<8,-> still has a non-negligible error, while posit<16,-> approximates almost perfectly the results obtained with the float format. In this case though, we've obtained the same timings for all the formats, which as already explained may be due to the smaller size of the operation: it would be therefore useful to run the test with bigger size to check if there is any difference in timing as the size of the matrix increases. Given the results obtained in this paper, we can conclude that the posit<8,-> is recommended only if we only care about the memory footprint and do not have particular requirements in terms of accuracy; if we do have requirements in terms of accuracy, we should instead use posit<16,->, which is better in accuracy with respect to BFLOAT16, achieving almost the same

accuracy of the float format but with a far smaller memory footprint.

4.3 Convolution

The tests we run on the convolution kernel are a bit different from the ones run for the other two operations: in this case, we still run the test on the same formats, but we only run a 3*3 convolution on squared layers of dimensions equal to 8, 16, 32, 64, 128 and 256, because the amount of operations and the computing time for the 256-dimensional case was comparable to the 2048-dimensional case for matrix multiplication, therefore running further test was impracticable using Google Colab. However, as for the fully connected operation we have a small memory footprint if we consider the 256-dimensional case, which results in basically no difference in the total computation timing, as shown in *Figure 13*.

Figure 13: Total time to get the result of the convolution

We can see from *Figure 13* that the time looks the same for all the formats, but since it scales exponentially from this point on making tests would require too high computational power which Google Colab does not provide.

In fact, we can see from *Figure 14* that the memory footprint is even smaller than in the previous two cases, even if the total time required for the computation remains the same in the highest dimensional case. From the same picture, we can see that the proportion between the different formats continue to hold, but the amount of data moved between host and device is drastically lower since in this case we have only to move a 3*3 matrix (the kernel) and two 256*256 matrix corresponding to the two layers.

For what concerns Operands Transfer Time, Result Transfer Time and Compute Time for the convolution, the results remain consistent with the ones already saw in the two previous operations, therefore the graphs are not reported here since they do not add anything that hasn't already been shown.

As for the average error, the results are once again similar to the previous cases: the main difference in this case is that the best performing posit with 8 bit encoding is the one with a maximum of 2 bits reserved for the exponent, even if the difference is not particularly high in all cases. The graph for the error

Figure 14: Memory footprint of the convolution

is reported in *Figure 15* and seems to show that the error for posit<16,->, BFloat16 and floats is the same in all cases: however, this is due to the scale of the graph, which do not allow to see the difference between the three formats due to the presence of the error of posit<8,->.

Figure 15: Average error on the result of the convolution

In reality, of course float has no error, but there's a substantial difference between the error of BFloat16, which is in the interval $[0.00150, 0.00159]$, and posit<16,->, which is in the interval $[0.00018, 0.00022]$: there is in fact an order of magnitude of difference, with posit<16,-> performing better than BFloat16. This is actually the same order of magnitude of difference we have in the previous cases, but here it is not possible to see it due to the resolution of the graph.

We can therefore draw for the convolution operation the exact same conclusions we had for the fully connected operation: posit<16,-> seems to be the best format in this case, but it may be useful to study bigger dimensions to see if there is any difference in the time required as the memory footprint grows.

5 Conclusions

In this project we showed how to implement posits and BFLOAT16 in a C++ CUDA program in order to exploit them to perform some classical parallel operations as the matrix multiplication, fully connected multiplication and convolution. From the results we obtained, it is clear that alternative formats have a great advantage against classical floats, since they are able to obtain a very good accuracy with less bits in the same amount of time; on the other hand, we need to be careful on the format itself, since we may have drastic drops in accuracy, as in the case of `posit<8,->`, which may not be sustainable depending on the application domain.

Even if these formats already proved their worthiness with the tests we performed, it is important to highlight that we were only testing their capabilities in terms of memory footprint and accuracy in this case, due to the lack of hardware support from the GPUs provided by Google Colab, which had no support for posits at all and slightly outdated support to BFLOAT16 too. Following studies should therefore focus on the usage of posits and BFLOAT16 in presence of the correct hardware support, with a PPU for posits and the most updated hardware for BFLOAT16: in such case, it could be interesting to see the behavior of `posit<32,->` as well, which has not been tested in this project since the memory footprint would've been the same as the one of the float format, with an error basically equal to zero and a computation time equal to the one of the float case since we would've had to perform the conversion to perform the operations.